

Electrochemical oxidation of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in landfill leachate: A short review

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Abstract

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are persistent pollutants found in landfill leachate, posing significant risks to environment and human health. Conventional treatment methods, such as adsorption and membrane filtration, have limitations of secondary waste generation as a phase separation technique. Electrochemical oxidation (EO) has gained attention as a promising approach for PFAS removal. This review examines the sources of PFAS in landfill leachate. Further, the review evaluates the performance of EO processes in degrading PFAS compounds in landfill leachate, but concerns such as toxic by-product formation remain. The study describes the influencing parameters that affect the process efficiency and mechanism of degradation. Future research directions focus on optimizing electrode materials and hybrid treatment approaches to enhance sustainability and obtain complete PFAS removal from landfill leachate.

Keywords

Electrochemical oxidation; electrode; landfill leachate; wastewater treatment; Sustainability

1. Introduction

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are commonly used in various consumer goods and industrial products owing to excellent thermal and chemical stability (Yan et al., 2015). However, these chemicals are persistent in nature and are of serious environmental concerns due to its bioaccumulation potential and may cause neurotoxicity, immunotoxicity, and carcinogenicity (Ahrens and Bundschuh, 2014). United States Environmental Protection Agency has advised a limit of 0.07 µg/L in drinking water for perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS), the two commonly studied compounds out of 3000 PFAS identified (US EPA, 2016a, b; Wei et al., 2019). Multiple PFAS has been detected in landfill leachate with a varying concentration range. Conventional methods such as adsorption and membrane filtration has the disadvantages of high operational cost and secondary waste generation. Electrochemical oxidation (EO), a degradation process can mineralize PFAS into fluoride ions and carbon dioxide, reducing the overall impacts on environment (Maldonado et al., 2021). This review evaluates the effectiveness of EO in PFAS degradation, focusing on electrode materials, operational parameters, efficiency, and disadvantages.

2. Sources of PFAS in landfill leachate

Landfill leachate is a significant reservoir of PFAS. The sources of PFAS are food packaging products, household consumer good, cosmetic products, electronic component, construction and demolition waste, industrial waste, incinerator ash, bio solids, and manufacturing waste. The waste landed up in landfills and degrade over time which leach PFAS into landfill leachate. Higher concentration of PFAS concentration has been reported in paper food packaging, fast food wrappers, plastic wrap, and ready-to-microwave popcorn bags. Household consumer goods such as cleaning products, non-stick cookware, stain-resistant fabrics, utensils, carpets,

and waterproof clothing may contribute to PFAS in landfill leachate. Cosmetic products in which the anti-statics, emulsifiers, stabilizers, viscosity regulators, film formers, surfactants, and solvents are used may also contribute to PFAS significantly. PFAS may find their way in landfill leachate as part of semiconductors, mobile devices, circuit boards, and electrical insulation wire and cable. Construction and demolition waste, for example, asphalt, concrete, metals, mixed wood, debris can also be sources. Industries use PFAS in products such as textiles, paper, coatings, and plastics to increase the products' heat, chemical and stain resistance and to increase the durability. PFAS-containing biosolids and incineration ash are often disposed of in landfills. Additionally, wastewater treatment plant residues, particularly sludge and effluents, serve as indirect PFAS contributors when disposed of in landfills (Singh et al., 2025; Tolaymat et al., 2023). Given their chemical stability and mobility, PFAS persist in leachate, necessitating advanced treatment technologies for effective removal.

3. Efficiency of EO in PFAS Degradation

Pierpaoli et al. (2021) studied the removal of PFOA and PFOS using boron-doped diamond electrode from landfill leachate and phosphate buffer. 78 to 80% removal efficiency was achieved in landfill leachate whereas higher removal efficiency of 83 to 99% was achieved for phosphate buffer. A flow-through EO cell is used for the degradation of perfluoroalkyl acids ranging from 10^2 to 10^4 ng/L in six different landfill leachate samples using boron-doped diamond electrode and the maximum observed removal efficiency was 73.5% (Maldonado et al., 2021). Duinslaeger et al. (2023) compared between borophene-doped and boron-doped graphene sponge anode where borophene-doped graphene sponge anode exhibited higher removal efficiency of 95 and 75% for PFOS and PFOA, respectively.

4. Influencing parameters

The effect of current density and electrode material composition was monitored by Pierpaoli et al. (2021). At higher current density of 75 mA/cm^2 , 78% and 80% removal efficiencies were achieved whereas lowering the current density to 25 mA/cm^2 reduced the efficiency by half. This was due to higher generation of reactive oxygen species. The study also investigated boron doping level of 0.5k and 10k and observed comparable removal efficiencies. In another study, current density was varied from 50 to 200 mA/cm^2 for perfluoroalkyl acids removal in landfill leachates. More than 97% degradation of PFOA and PFOS was achieved within 2 hours at 150 mA/cm^2 of electrochemical oxidation using boron-doped diamond anode (Maldonado et al., 2021). The influence of electrode material on PFAS degradation was studied by Duinslaeger et al. (2023). The use of a borophene-functionalized reduced graphene oxide anode improved PFAS removal efficiency, achieving 77% for PFOS and 57% for PFOA, compared to 69% and 41% with a standard boron-doped graphene sponge anode, respectively.

5. Mechanism

Electrochemical oxidation can degrade PFAS through direct and indirect oxidation pathways. PFAS degradation is initiated by direct electron transfer forming perfluoroalkyl radicals. The so formed radical then reacts with electrochemically generated hydroxyl radical, $\bullet\text{OH}$ and shorter-chain PFAS will be formed through a chain of reaction. Both direct and indirect oxidation will take part till complete mineralization takes place (Maldonado et al., 2021). Pierpaoli et al. (2021) reported a multi-step mechanism for PFOA degradation which involves electron transfer, Kolbe decarboxylation, radical reactions, and hydroxylation. PFOA radicals form by direct electron transfer. These radicals are highly unstable and undergo Kolbe decarboxylation forming CO_2 and perfluoroheptyl radicals. The radicals react with O_2

generating C₇F₁₅• radicals which further decomposed into carbonyl fluoride and perfluorohexyl radicals. Hydrolysis of carbonyl fluoride produced CO₂ and HF making the onset of defluorination. The electrochemical degradation of PFOS is also a multi-step mechanism involving radical reactions, Kolbe decarboxylation, hydrolysis, and hydroxylation. First, PFOS goes for fluoride ion elimination. Hydroxyl radical further oxidize and perfluoroheptyl sulphate radicals is formed via hydrolysis and Kolbe decarboxylation. The radicals then react with oxygen generating perfluoroalkoxy intermediates, which decompose into perfluorohexyl sulphate radicals and carbonyl fluoride. Carbonyl fluoride will then form CO₂ and HF indicating defluorination via hydrolysis (Pierpaoli et al., 2021).

The major challenge of the EO process is the formation of by-products like short-chain perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs) and halogenated transformation products. Incomplete defluorination may lead to persistent intermediates generation such as perfluorobutanoic acid and perfluoropentanoic acid which exhibits higher mobility and significant environmental risk (Rehnstam et al., 2024).

6. Conclusion

Electrochemical oxidation is a promising technology for the degradation of PFAS compounds present in landfill leachate. Although, the process showed significant removal efficiency of PFAS compounds, limited studies are available to understand the overall performance of the process. Incomplete mineralization may contribute to intermediates formation having severe characteristics than the parent compounds from environmental risk perspective. Therefore, electrode materials and the process parameters need to be optimized further to understand the way of achieving complete mineralization and minimal by-products formation. Overall, the electrochemical oxidation process could be proven efficient for PFAS degradation in landfill leachate. Further, the integration of EO with biological treatment technologies can enhance sustainability and reduce energy consumption.

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